

HEALTHY 02

Lifestyle and therapy

Healthy and affordable eating, exercising, safe use of medication and wellness therapies

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of Technology

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HEALTHY MODULE 2

Lifestyle and therapy

This module gives you some tips about healthy and affordable eating, exercising, safe use of medication and wellness therapies. By the end of this unit, you'll know more about these topics, and you'll be one step closer to becoming a facilitator in your community when it comes to the uptake of a healthier lifestyle!

What will you learn

- 1 What is healthy eating
- 2 Tips for daily and weekly planning of nutritionally balanced meals
- 3 Tips for eating healthy on a budget
- 4 Exercise: Tips for adults aged 19 to 64 and adults aged 65 and over
- 5 Safe use of medication and questions for your healthcare providers on your next visit
- 6 The role of the community: support in the neighbourhood and wellness therapies to engage with others in the community

Chapters in this module

1

How to keep a healthy diet

2

How to eat healthy on a budget

3

How to exercise more often

4

Safe use of medication

5

Wellness therapies

HEALTHY

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 1

How to keep a healthy diet

What is Healthy Eating? In this chapter you will learn more about this topic and we will give you some tips for daily and weekly planning of nutritionally balanced meals. Are you ready to embark on this journey?

Let's do this!

How to keep a healthy diet

- 4.1 million annual deaths have been attributed to excess salt/sodium intake
- 1.6 million deaths annually can be attributed to insufficient physical activity

An unhealthy diet can increase the risk of dying from a Chronic Disease.

The good news? You can help to prevent chronic diseases by making positive diet and lifestyle changes, that can help reduce risk.

Will you join us in this quest and bring others along with you?

What will you learn

- 1 Fruits and vegetables: how many times a day?
- 2 The role of starchy foods in a healthy diet
- 3 Healthy diet with more fish
- 4 Tips to eat less saturated fat and sugar
- 5 Water intake: how much water should you be drinking per day?
- 6 Some facts about salt and sugar

Meet Maria, 84, Spain

Maria likes taking care of her children, June and Jon

She likes knitting, watching soap operas on TV, feeding pigeons dry breadcrumbs in the park

Maria lives in a flat on the 3rd floor with no central heating and no lift

Her pension is little, and her family is having serious financial difficulties

She has very low health literacy levels, so we would like to help her! Will you join us? Let's start by learning more about "How to keep a healthy diet"!

How to keep a healthy diet

1**2****3**

Eat fruit and vegetables

Eat at least 5 portions of a variety of fruit and vegetables every day. They can come in all sizes and shapes: fresh, frozen, canned, dried or juiced! Favour fresh and frozen portions of fruit or vegetables and limit consumption of save canned, dried or juices.

Did you know?

Juicing releases the sugars in the fruit, which can damage teeth. On top of that, they lack fiber, so we end up absorbing the fruit juice as we would any other sugary drinks. Even unsweetened fruit juice and smoothies are sugary.

Go for the soup!

It is a healthy and tasty way of consuming vegetables and keeping a healthy diet. Try to include vegetables in your recipes - they are a cheap and healthy way to add flavour, colour and aroma to your dishes!

How to keep a healthy diet

1

2

3

Base your meals on starchy foods

Including potatoes, bread, rice, pasta and low-sugar cereals, ex: rolled oats or cornflakes. Favour higher fibre or wholegrain varieties, ex: brown rice, wholewheat pasta or potatoes with their skins on. Try to have at least one of them in each main meal!

How to keep a healthy diet

1

2

3

Eat more fish and reduce your meat eating

You should try to eat at least 3/4 portions of fish a week. This should include at least 1 portion of oily fish: salmon, tuna, trout, herring, sardines or mackerel, for example.

How to keep a healthy diet

4

5

6

Cut down on saturated fat

You need some fat in your diet, but it's important to pay attention to the amount and type of fat you're eating. For example: fatty cuts of meat, butter, lard, cream, sour cream and ice cream, biscuits, cakes, and pastries. Save these for special occasions!

Did you know?

Ready-meals have a lot of fat, especially saturated fat.

That is why you should avoid eating these everyday.

There are other ways to save time and money and still eat healthy. Stay tuned because there's still more to come in the next chapter "**How to eat healthy on a budget**" !

Remember

Limit the amount of fried food and high fat roasts. Besides being bad for our health, they use more resources (gas and fat for frying) and end you end up with a bigger pile of dirty dishes!

Did you know?

In the case of canned products with fat (e.g. tuna, sardines), drain the fat very well before using. Or prefer the options in water. This will reduce the amount of fat added to the dish!

How to keep a healthy diet

4

5

6

Reach your daily water goal (recommended 1,5l/2l)

Drink it (daily) plain, sparkling or with a slice of lemon or lime! Try making some tea. Drink it while it's hot or leave in the refrigerator to chill (Hello, Summer!) Don't add sugar. If you're used to it, try to gradually reduce the sugar amount, until you stop using it.

Here's a tip

You should be drinking your daily dose of 1,5l/2l water but are you having trouble doing so?

Get into the habit of carrying your 750ml water bottle with you and fill it every morning. Set your goal: drink one full bottle in the morning and one in the afternoon!

OR get a little help from technology and download a Daily Water Tracker & Reminder Mobile app, for example. [Waterminder](#).

What do you think? Let's stay hydrated!

How to keep a healthy diet

4

5

6

Eat less salt and sugar

Sugar is that you? Take a closer look at the food labels and discover sugar's many guises: sucrose, glucose, fructose, maltose, fruit juice, molasses, hydrolysed starch, invert sugar, corn syrup, honey!

Cut down on salt!

WHO recommends that adults consume less than 5 g of salt per day. That's just under a teaspoon.

Most people consume on average 9–12 grams per day. That's too much salt!

What happens if your salt intake is less than 5 grams per day for adults?

It helps to reduce:

- blood pressure
- risk of cardiovascular disease, stroke and coronary heart attack

Did you know?

It is estimated that 2.5 million deaths globally could be prevented each year if global salt consumption were reduced to the recommended level.

Cut down on salt!

Here are some tips to help you reduce your salt intake:

During the preparation of food

Make the most of fresh herbs, spices, lemon juice, wine and vinegar. Use them to season your cooking. Put the saltshaker away to avoid the urge to add more salt!

At the table

Don't bring the salt shaker with you to the table. Out of sight, out of mind!

On the go

Eat less salty snacks (chips, salted crackers and salted nuts). Favour natural peanuts and leave the salted ones for a special occasion.

Be careful

Whenever you use canned food in your meal (e.g. peeled tomatoes, beans, chickpeas, peas, etc), you need to substantially reduce the amount of salt added, as canned food already has salt in its composition. In the cases where the broth can be drained (e.g. chickpeas, beans), drain and wash well before using to remove excess salt.

How many salt is there?

“Foods high in salt taste salty.” This should not lead you to believe that all foods high in salt taste salty. Here are some examples!

In a plate of instant noodles

2 coffee spoons of salt. That's close to 5 grams of salt. Remember WHO's recommendation? 5 g of salt per day! One quick lunch and you already go beyond the daily recommendation!

In a frozen pizza

2 tablespoons of salt. That's 3,6 grams of salt! How about trying a new homemade recipe for pizza?

In a ready meal microwave lasagna

2 tablespoons of salt! That's 3,9 grams of salt, only one 1g left to reach the recommended salt intake!

Cut down on salt!

There's salt in many products you may be forgetting about. Here are a few of them:

- ✓ Processed foods (such as ready meals)
 - ✓ Processed meats like bacon, ham, salami, and sausages
 - ✓ Cheese, salty snack foods, and instant noodles, among others
 - ✓ Soy sauce, fish sauce
 - ✓ Broth concentrate
 - ✓ Canned seafood, fish and meat
- ✓ Remember the overheard saying? “Foods high in salt taste salty.” You just saw that this isn’t a rule. This advice also holds true for sugar: just because it doesn’t taste sweet, doesn’t mean it doesn’t have sugar in it! Next, you will learn some facts about sugar. Let’s go!

Let's talk about sugar!

Excessive sugar consumption plays a key role in promoting overweight and obesity, diabetes and tooth decay.

Sugar is available in most foods and sugar-sweetened beverages (soft drinks, for example), sugary snacks and sweets.

The list includes: ice cream cakes, biscuits, breakfast cereals, chocolates, candied fruit, chocolate powder, jams and marmalade, sweetened yoghurt, some plant-based milk (some soy and rice drinks, for example) and honey.

Did you know?

Any sugars that were added to food or drinks are called free sugars. These sugars may be added by a food manufacturer, at home, or by a chef.

The sugars in honey, syrups (such as maple, agave), and unsweetened fruit juices, vegetable juices and smoothies occur naturally but still count as free sugars.

Adults should have no more than 30g of free sugars a day!

Did you know?

Sugar found naturally in fruit and vegetables, and milk does not count as free sugars.

We do not need to cut down on these sugars.

But they are included in the "total sugar" figure found on food labels!

How many sugar is there?

Remember the phrase “Foods high in salt taste salty”? The same applies to sugar!

In 4 chocolate chip cookies

24 g of sugar. That's roughly 2 tablespoons of sugar!

In a coke bottle

30g of sugar! That's close to 2 tablespoons of sugar!

In a chocolate milk box

20g of sugar. That's 1,5 tablespoons!

On Balance

These foods should not be banned from your diet.

Instead, save them for special occasions (a weekend night out/in with your friends, for example)!

Hands full and hands-on: list of useful contacts and services

Before you go on to the next chapter, be sure to browse some of these links with some useful materials and services to help you continue with your learning!

Traffic light labels to decode nutritional information

What's in a label? Find out more about your salt and sugar consumption by taking a close look at the food labels:

- ✓ <https://alimentacaosaudavel.dgs.pt/descodificador-de-rotulos/> (PT)

Healthy Recipes

Let's get cooking! Here are some healthy recipes for you to try today:

- ✓ <https://alimentacaosaudavel.dgs.pt/receitas/> (PT)
- ✓ <https://www.bluezones.com/recipes/> (EN)

Chapter summary

1

You have learned the recommend portion of fruit and vegetables you should be eating every day

2

You have learned the role of starchy foods in a healthy diet

3

Do you feel ready to eat less meat? A healthy diet should include more fish than meat

4

Cut down on saturated fat and sugar: remember this on your next trip to the supermarket

5

Grab you water bottle! By now you should be increasing your daily water intake

6

You've gone through some facts about salt and sugar. How do you feel about that?

7

Head over to the next chapters to learn more about other topics that create a healthy lifestyle

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1 How to keep a healthy diet

- 2 Tips to reduce salt and sugar intake.
Recommended water intake

- 3 Knowledge is power: share this outcomes
with Maria and others in your community

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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HEALTHY

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 2

How to eat healthy on a budget

Do you want to eat Healthy on a budget? Do you know someone that is having trouble keeping a varied diet? This chapter is for you! We'll go over some things to have in mind when planning your next visit to the supermarket, ways to reduce food waste, and energy saving tips. Shall we begin?

How to eat healthy on a budget

This chapter is here to give you healthy, tasty and budget cooking tips.

Eat healthy and well-balanced meals today!

What will you learn

- 1 Plan the next visit to the supermarket
- 2 How to reduce food waste
- 3 How to turn leftovers into new meals
- 4 Energy saving tips
- 5 Where to buy cheaper meals and ingredients
- 6 New recipes to cook what's in season

Meet Maria, 84, Spain

Maria likes to cook, but has difficulties doing the groceries as well as cooking meals (that are healthy and well-balanced)

How to eat healthy on a budget

What are some of her needs?

Her pension is little, and her family is having serious financial difficulties.

How can she eat healthier on a tight budget?

Remember, this advice is helpful for Maria and everyone who would like to save money and resources!

[More](#)

Reducing food waste

Here are some meal prep ideas and some tips to have in mind when grocery shopping!

Plan the week's meals in advance

Choose a day of the week to plan the meals and make a shopping list. This way it'll be easier to incorporate this into your routine!

In the supermarket

Stick to the plan and avoid impulsive buying! Pay attention to expiry dates. Frozen food should be the last item to be included in the shopping trolley.

Four seasons

Go for what's in season: it's cheaper, nutritious and less harmful to the environment!

Reducing food waste

It is estimated that 25% of food purchased currently goes to waste! What can we do to avoid it?

It's all about the peel

Try to eat fruit and vegetables with their peel whenever it's possible. It's packed with fibre, vitamin and minerals!

Use it all

You can avoid food waste by using old leaves and stems as a basis for your next soup!

Be creative

You can use ripe fruit to make purées, juices or smoothies. You can add it to yoghurt or include it in some recipes (e.g., pancakes, cakes)

Did you know?

If you reuse the cooking stocks (of vegetables, fish, etc.) together with some herbs, you can substantially reduce the amount of salt added to the dish.

Healthier outcomes that are also good for your wallet!

Reducing food waste

The list isn't over yet! Here are some more tips:

Dress up your stock

Don't waste the leftover cooking water! These broths contain a lot of vitamins, minerals, fibres. They can be used to make a soup or as a base for cooking rice, pasta, stews, etc.

Plan, plan, plan

To avoid wasting vegetables, fruit, and other fresh produce, buy only the amount necessary to prepare the meals that you plan to have for the day/week.

Plan, plan, plan Part II

If you're buying large quantities of food, try to anticipate if you can consume all of it before the expiry date. "Best before by" relates to food quality and is not the same as "use-by" that relates to food safety.

Reducing food waste

Turn leftovers into new meals! Here are some suggestions:

Reinvent yourself and your food

If you're left with leftovers - pack and store them in the refrigerator for up to 3 days (72h). You can just reheat them or use them to make other dishes!

Meat and Fish leftovers

Leftover meat and fish can be used shredded and added to dishes such as salads, pies, pasta, rice, sandwiches, etc.

Cooked potatoes/vegetables

Cooked potato/ vegetables can be included in soups, purées, etc.

Vegetables can also be added to other dishes - e.g. rice or pasta.

Reducing food waste

Turn leftovers into new meals! Here are some suggestions:

Leftover beans, chickpeas, etc

Cooked pulses (e.g. beans, chickpeas) can be added to the base of soups salads or included in various dishes (e.g. bean rice, pasta with chickpeas, etc).

Leftover bread

Bread can be used to make toasts, bread pudding, breadcrumbs (put the bread in the oven to dry and mince it after that!)

Fruit juice

Fruit juice (e.g. orange, lemon, apple) can be used to make tea or flavoured waters. Remember to reach your daily water goal (recommended 1,5l/2l)

Our tip

Do you live alone? Pair up with your neighbour and share food that goes off quickly, for example split a pineapple in half and hand it over to your neighbour!

This tip is useful for other things besides food. Do you have a garden but don't need to have tools of your own? Why don't you buy new ones together with your next door neighbour? They can also be useful for a community garden. Stay tuned, because there's more to come on this topic in chapter "**Wellness therapies**"!

Energy saving tips

Now, what can we do to save more money while cooking? Here are a tips to help your budget and the environment!

The heat is off

When cooking, turn off the heat source 5 to 10 minutes before finish cooking. There's still enough heat to finish cooking the food.

Under pressure

Cooking in a pressure cooker can be an option for faster, healthier cooking, and with less water.

Cook extra servings at a time

Freeze/refrigerate the extra servings for later - especially on days when you have less time to cook. This way, you'll save energy (gas, electricity), water and time.

Energy saving tips: Cooker

- Use pans that are the right size for the amount of food you are cooking
- Put lids on pans to prevent heat loss
- Match the size of the pan to the size of the gas burner to make the most of the heat
- When you reach the desired temperature (e.g., boiling), lower the heat and let it simmer

Energy saving tips: Oven

- Keep the oven closed while cooking - constantly opening the oven causes the oven to lose heat and use extra energy to recover from it
- Don't preheat the oven for longer than necessary. Many ovens need only a few minutes to reach cooking temperatures
- If the oven is electric, switch it off 5 to 10 minutes before the cooking time is up
- Glass/ceramic cookware is more efficient than metal pans. It allows cooking at a lower temperature

Did you know?

The microwave is the most energy-efficient appliance, followed by the cooker and then the oven . The latter uses the most energy.

If you have electric appliances such as a kettle or toaster available, use them instead of the cooker. **They use less energy**

More energy saving tips!

Here are some other tips to help you save money while cooking healthy meals:

- ✓ Defrosting food properly cuts the cooking time in half.
How can you do this? Gradually, in the refrigerator, using the Microwave or in running, cold water.
- ✓ Cutting food into smaller reduces cooking time
- ✓ Keeping the cooker and oven clean allows for greater energy efficiency
- ✓ Use only as much water as necessary to cook your food
- ✓ Whenever possible, cook more than one food at the same time (e.g., cook fish, potatoes and vegetables all in the same pot)

Hands full and hands-on: list of useful contacts and services

Before you go on to the next chapter, be sure to browse some of these links with some useful materials and services to help you continue with your learning!

What's in season

Find out what fruits and vegetables are in season in your country:

- ✓ <https://alimentacaosaudavel.dgs.pt/receitas/> (PT)
- ✓ <https://www.bordbia.ie/whats-in-season/> (IE)
- ✓ <https://eatsmarter.de/saisonkalender> (DE)
- ✓ EetBewust (jouwweb.nl) (NL)

Zero Waste

Find out more about this places that sell food and other goods at lower prizes:

- ✓ <https://toogoodtogo.pt/pt> (PT)
- ✓ <https://goodafter.com/pt/> (PT)

Activity 1: What's in season?

Make good use of what's in season!

You just found out what fruits and vegetables are in season in your country! What about learning some new recipes? Let's pick one!

Let's go with pumpkin!

Did you know that in Portugal pumpkin season takes place during autumn and winter months? And in your country? What did you find out?

[More](#)

We're making dreams come true!

Have you heard about the Portuguese dessert “*Sonhos*”? The word literally means “Dreams”! They are very popular on Christmas. One of the traditional recipes consists of fried pumpkin cakes, but we will give you a healthier oven-baked [recipe](#) to try out once it's pumpkin season!

Remember: eating right is about balance, so desserts can be part of the menu, even if just once in a while. Save them for special occasions (for example, the weekend) !

I'm dreaming of: Sonhos de Abóbora (Pumpkin cakes)

- 1 kg of pumpkin;
- 4 eggs;
- 250 grams of oat flour, spelt or wheat flour
- ½ dl of milk (dairy or plant-based milk);
- Lemon or orange zest;
- Four tablespoons of brown or coconut sugar
- Two teaspoons of baking powder
- Cinnamon powder (to taste)
- Honey (to taste)

Start by cooking the pumpkin in a pot with water and salt.

Once cooked, let it drain overnight (you can use a sieve with a cloth and place the pumpkin on it).

The next day, mash the pumpkin and add all the ingredients, namely the egg yolks, the flour with the baking powder, the milk, the lemon/orange zest and the sugar.

Finally, beat the egg whites until stiff and add to the mixture. But be careful: stir from bottom to top so that the mixture becomes fluffy. Let it rest for 30 minutes.

Preheat the oven to 160 degrees C°.

In a muffin tin, fill the tins with baking paper. Pour spoonfuls of the batter until almost full. Bake for 15 to 20 minutes.

At the end, you have three options:

- Sprinkle the cakes with cinnamon and drizzle them with honey;
- Coat the cakes in a mixture of cinnamon and coconut sugar;
- Or make a Port wine syrup with a little water and honey (to taste) - let it boil for a while and drizzle this syrup in the cakes!

What do you think?

Do you like this recipe? Give it a try once it's pumpkin season in your country!

And while you're at it, save this recipe in a recipe book and share with others you think might be interested in them (a friend, a family member, a neighbour!) Did you know that you can do that online? Do you run a grocery shop? Why not start having recipes in the store for ingredients in season?

Remember Maria?

Encourage others like her to join you in your quest for a healthier lifestyle!

Invite friends over for a healthy night out

Why not get together with your friends/neighbours every two weeks to exchange some healthy tips and recipes?

Share your healthy recipes with your friends

Spread the news and healthy tips: share new recipes with your contacts

Engage with others in the community

Did you feel encouraged to try a new recipe with a vegetable that's in season? Set aside a piece and go over to your neighbour's!

Make a videocall and share the results

Distance doesn't make the heart grow fonder! Make some time once a week to contact your family, and friends. Send them pictures of your pumpkin cakes!

Chapter summary

1

By now, you have an array of tips that will be helpful to plan the next week's meals in advance

2

Headed to the supermarket? Take our tips with you, give it a try

3

Eat what's in season: cheap, nutritious and green options for you to try today

4

Reduce food waste: plan your meals, (re) use it all

5

At the kitchen: Energy saving tips cooker and oven

6

Hands full and hands on: list of fruits and vegetables in season and zero waste services

7

Let's get cooking: Healthy and cheap recipes

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1 How to go for cheaper and healthier options

- 2 How to reduce food waste

- 3 How to save energy while cooking

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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HEALTHY

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 3

How to exercise more often

Staying active is key to a Healthy lifestyle. What are your exercise habits? Would you like to workout more? This is a chance to learn more about exercise and boost your health literacy! This chapter goes over some tips to stay active in all ages! Let's get going? Hop in!

Exercise and physical activity

- Physical activity is good for your heart, body and mind
- It helps to prevent and manage noncommunicable diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, cancer and diabetes
- It reduces symptoms of depression and anxiety
- It enhances thinking, learning, and judgment skills
- Physical activity improves overall well-being

What will you learn

- 1 What counts as exercise and physical activity
- 2 How to exercise more often
- 3 How can you workout in groups
- 4 How to engage with neighbours and be more active in the community

Did you know?

Up to 5 million deaths a year could be prevented if the global population was more active.

People who are insufficiently active have a 20% to 30% increased risk of death compared to people who are sufficiently active.

More than 80% of the world's adolescent population is insufficiently physically active.

Meet Teresa, 83, Portugal

- She likes walking in the public garden near her home everyday
- She goes to classes 3 times a week in a university of the third age and likes participating in social Porto city initiatives
- She likes being independent

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 3**

You've got to know a little bit about Teresa now and you can see that she's an active person!
What about you?
What is your exercise routine like?
Check off the items of the list!

- I am part of a walking group
- I take dance classes
- I go the gym every week
- I am not physically active
- I am physically active
- Activities of daily living like cooking, cleaning, going to the supermarket, are the only exercise in my routine
- I walk to work everyday
- I would be more physically active if I had someone to join me

How to exercise more often

Now that you've thought about your exercise habits, let's go over some key facts about exercising:

- ✓ Any type of activity is good for you
- ✓ The more you do the better
- ✓ You can do your weekly goal of physical activity on a single day or over 2 or more days
- ✓ Adults should do some type of physical activity every day
- ✓ **How can you implement these changes in your routine? Or, if you're already an active person, how can you encourage others to do the same? Let's find out!**

How to exercise more often

Here are some tips for adults aged 19 to 64! These physical activity guidelines are according to the NHS, that is why we present you with tips for two different groups: adults aged 19 to 64 and older adults aged 65 and over. Nevertheless, keep in mind that everyone is unique and must follow what's best for them! Let's go!

Find what you care about

There are plenty of ways to get going! Find out what's best for you: a walk in the park, the beach, the mountains, whichever your surroundings are; swimming; dancing, team sports; jogging; the list is never ending!

Implement changes in your routine

You can do your weekly goal of physical activity on a single day or over 2 or more days. Pick a day of the week to do that. Mark that on your agenda! You're always on time to take up a new habit!

Make your life easier while doing it

Leave your running shoes by the door. Pack your bags the evening before. Invite a friend to join. These actions help you stay focused and go on with your plans!

How to exercise more often: Moderate activity

Go for a walk
It will raise your heart rate

Enjoy a bike ride
It will make you breathe faster
and feel warmer

Push a lawn mower
If you're working at a
moderate intensity level, you
can still talk, but not sing. Try
it!

Dance!
Do at least 150 minutes of
moderate intensity activity a
week

How to exercise more often: Vigorous activity

Go for a jog

75 minutes of vigorous activity can give similar health benefits to 150 minutes of moderate intensity activity

Go for a swim

Most moderate activities can become vigorous if you increase your effort

Play some sports

Vigorous activity makes you breathe hard and fast

Walk up the stairs

You will not be able to say more than a few words without pausing for breath

Adults aged 65 and over are the most sedentary age group

How to exercise more often: Light activity

Getting up and making a cup of tea

What counts as light activity?
Moving rather than sitting or lying down!

Moving around the house
It's good to do light activity, even if it's just moving around the house!

Walking at a slow pace

Reduce time spent sitting or lying down.

Vacuuming

Any type of activity is better than none. And the more the merrier!

REMEMBER

There is no typical older person, so the previous recommendations don't apply to each individual from these age groups.

Find out what's best for you and understand that does not necessarily apply to everyone!

Let's get moving!

Be part of something

- Exercising in groups can be easier than working out alone. When we work out with other people, we also enjoy spending time with them. Everyone is there for the same purpose, so we value the companionship of others.
- Your workout buddies can become your family and this sense of camaraderie can help to create accountability!

“And that’s what I need: someone who is counting on me to show up “

Member of Blue Zones Project Walking Moais

<https://info.bluezonesproject.com/fw/moai/walking>

Find workout buddies!

You can go on daily walks throughout the neighborhood and encourage your neighbors to join!

In USA, for example, groups of 5 to 8 people gather once in a week to go for a stroll (at least 30 minutes) around the community.

This idea stemmed from Moai, a social mechanism from Okinawa, Japan, that brings groups of people together for a common purpose.

Be a change agent!

[Read more](#)

Night Runners Coimbra

- Night Runners Coimbra is a night run/walk group in Coimbra, Portugal
- A group of students of the Bachelor's Degree in ESEC started this project in 2013
- They bring people together in the streets and empower them to participate in this "Sport for All" initiative!
- The event is free, everyone can join, you just have to show up on Wednesdays at 9:30pm at the same meeting point!

Workout Groups in other countries

- <https://www.agoraporto.pt/programas/no-porto-a-vida-e-longa> (PT)
- [Dante is sportmaatje: 'Het is leuk om elkaar een beetje te helpen' | NOS](#) (NL)

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 3**

Are there workout buddies in your own community?
Let's get into it!
Do some quick research and share your findings below!

Activity 2: Find your workout buddies!

- Are you interested in the idea of having a workout buddy? They can go with you just for a walk around the park!
- Think for a minute, who would want to join you? A close friend, a relative, a neighbour? Or would you like to meet new people? Pick a person who you think would like to join you and invite them for a walk!
- You've met Teresa. She walks in the public garden near her home everyday. Follow her lead!

Chapter summary

1

Moderate activity, vigorous activity and light activity. It's all about being active

2

Hands full and hands on: list of workout groups in your country and community

3

Find your workout buddies!

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1 Tips to be more physically active

- 2 Types of exercise

- 3 Ways to find a workout buddy

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

HEALTHY | **MODULE 2** | **CHAPTER 4**

Safe use of medication

The aim of this chapter is to provide all learners with the essential information needed to manage medication.

What will you learn

- 1 Brand names vs generics
- 2 Basic information on medicines
- 3 Possible questions for healthcare providers
- 4 List of contacts and services

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 4**

Let's start with this: do you know the difference between brand names and generics?

Brand name	The name of the active ingredient in the medicine
Generic name	Created by the pharmaceutical company that made the medicine

Safe use of medication: Brand name vs generics

Generics

For example, Aciclovir is the generic name of a medicine used to treat cold sores, chickenpox and shingles

Brand names

The company that makes acyclovir sells it under the brand name Zovirax

[More](#)

Safe use of medication: Brand name vs generics

So, what does this mean?

The Generic Version = Branded Version
They contain the same active ingredients- the part of the medicine that makes it work- so they are the same

Generic medication is usually cheaper
They are just as effective but cost far less. Think about when you go to the supermarket. The supermarket's own label is usually cheaper than the branded version!

Your prescription medication keeps changing?
This might be because you're being given the generic version rather than the branded one. In the end, you take a generic medicine the same way as a brand-name one, so choose what's best for your budget!

Safe use of medication: Essential information on medicines

These are a lot of medicines, right? We need to be careful to keep track of our medicines and use them safely. If we take them the wrong way or mix certain medication, it can be dangerous. Find out more about the medicines below:

Prescriptions

What you can get only with a doctor's prescription (for example, an asthma inhaler or pills to lower your cholesterol levels)

Over-the-counter pills, liquids or creams

What you can buy without a prescription (for example, pills for headaches)

Vitamins, eye drops, or dietary supplements

Make sure your doctor knows about ALL the medicines you take, that includes those prescribed by other doctors, vitamins, supplements, herbal remedies, and over-the-counter medicines you use occasionally

Safe use of medication: Essential information on medicines

You should always talk with your doctor, nurse or other healthcare provider about the medication you are taking. Here is some useful advice for when you are starting a new medication!

- ✓ Go over your allergies and any problems you have had with other medication, such as trouble breathing, indigestion, rashes, dizziness, or mood swings
- ✓ Find out whether you'll need to change or stop taking any of your other prescriptions or over-the-counter medication while using this new medicine
- ✓ Keep a list of all prescription medicines and over-the-counter remedies you take. Keep track of your medications!
- ✓ Write down any special instructions for how to take the medicine!
- ✓ Next, we will guide you through some of the questions to ask the doctor about a new medicine

Safe use of medication: Stay informed

1

2

3

Questions for your healthcare providers

What is the name of the medicine and why am I taking it?

What medical condition does this medicine treat?

Safe use of medication: Stay informed

1

2

3

Questions for your healthcare providers

How many times a day should I take it? At what time(s)?

If the box says take “4 times a day,” does that mean 4 times in 24 hours or 4 times during the daytime?

Safe use of medication: Stay informed

1

2

3

Questions for your healthcare providers

How much medicine should I take?

Should I take the medicine with food or not? Is there anything I should not eat or drink when taking this medicine?

Safe use of medication: Stay informed

4

5

6

Questions for your healthcare providers

How long will it take this medicine to work?

What side effects can I expect? What should I do if I have a problem?

Will I need a refill? How do I arrange that?

Safe use of medication: Stay informed

4

5

6

Questions for your healthcare providers

Will this medicine cause problems if I am taking other medicines?

Is it safe for me to drive while taking this medication?

Safe use of medication: Stay informed

4

5

6

Questions for your healthcare providers

When should I stop taking the medicine?

If I forget to take my medicine, what should I do?

 Don't forget!

Each time you visit your doctor, tell him or her about new medication you're taking, and be sure to ask if you still need to be on all of them.

Remember, you can always refer to the directions for use, in case you need to clarify anything!

Activity 3: Medication Management

- Maria has multiple chronic conditions and is prescribed many different medications
- Her pension is little, and her family is having serious financial difficulties
- She has problems managing her own health and adherence to treatment is poor
- How can she begin to solve some of these issues? Let's see!

Activity 3: Medication Management

First: What is Maria's current treatment: medicines, therapies, etc?

- ✓ 1 insulin injection daily for glucose control
- ✓ 1 pill to prevent stomach ulcers
- ✓ 1 pill to prevent blood clots
- ✓ 1 pill to prevent water retention
- ✓ 2 pills to control blood pressure
- ✓ 1 pill to lower cholesterol
- ✓ Painkillers for occasional joint pain

Activity 3: Medication Management

Maria is having a hard time taking her meds

She needs help better adhering to her prescription and avoiding undesired side effects. Encourage her to keep a **List of Medication**.

Organize the list

This sheet will help to keep track of useful information to bring to the next doctor's appointment. Go ahead, check the next slide!

[More](#)

Activity 3: Medication Management

Call to Action! The list includes topics such as: name of the medication, what is it for, 1st dose, the doctor's name, the colour/shape of the medicine, medication instructions and possible side effects.

Draw inspiration from the list in the previous slide and create one for yourself, give it a try! You can also create one for Maria using the available information.

Remember, this example is useful for you, whether you use this list to keep track of your medicines or use this advice to help an older adult or someone you know with their medication management.

Did you know?

In Portugal and Ireland, there's a blister packing service in the pharmacy to help you (or the person you care for) keep track of the medication.

You can ask for information on this service at your local pharmacy and if you agree, they will start distributing your weekly medication into trays with separate compartments for the days of the week and times of day. Do you find this useful for you or someone you know?

Hands full and hands-on: list of useful contacts and services

Did you know that you can help to monitor the safety of medicines by reporting any suspected side effects?

Or get access to a database of medications and do a quick research on the prices? See the list below:

- ✓ Portugal, INFARMED - Autoridade Nacional do Medicamento e Produtos de Saúde, I. P. :
<https://www.infarmed.pt/web/infarmed> (PT)
- ✓ Ireland, Health Products Regulatory Authority (HPRA):
<https://www.hpra.ie/> (EN)
- ✓ Germany, Bundesinstitut für Arzneimittel und Medizinprodukte (BfArM):
https://www.bfarm.de/DE/Home/home_node.html (DE)
- ✓ Netherlands, College ter Beoordeling van Geneesmiddelen (CBG): <https://www.cbg-meb.nl/onderdelen/over-cbg> (NL)
- ✓ France, L'Agence nationale de sécurité du médicament et des produits de santé (ANSM),
<https://www.ansm.sante.fr/>
- ✓ Poland, <http://www.urpl.gov.pl/pl> (PL)

Hands full and hands-on: list of useful contacts and services

Before you go on to the next chapter, be sure to browse some of these links with some useful materials and services to help you continue with your learning!

Electronic Medical Prescription

- ✓ <https://www.sns24.gov.pt/servico/aceder-a-receita/>
(PT)
- ✓ [Electronisch voorschrijven \(EVS\) | Medicatieveiligheid | Inspectie Gezondheidszorg en Jeugd \(igj.nl\)](#) (NL)

Board Game about the safe use of medication

Tratar de Mim, or in English, Taking care of Myself, is a board game designed in Portugal for children from 7 to 12 years old to improve their health in a fun way. It is available for (free) download here:

<https://extranet.apifarma.pt/tratardemim/Paginas/Jogo-Tratar-de-Mim.aspx>

Chapter summary

1

By now, you should know difference between brand names and generics

2

You've gone over some essential information on medicines

3

You've learnt some useful questions on medication to ask healthcare providers

4

You have a list of useful contacts and services

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

What's the difference between brand name and generics

2

What to ask on the next doctor's appointment

3

How to keep track of the medication

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

HEALTHY

MODULE 2

CHAPTER 5

Wellness therapies

This chapter focus on holistic therapies and the role of the community in Healthy Ageing.

Wellness of mind and body

- A wellness therapy focusses on the mental and physical health of the individual.
- Building and maintaining relationships also contributes to a healthy lifestyle.
- Stay tuned and learn more about yoga, tai chi, painting, dance classes, and other group activities that improve your lifestyle and will enable you to be and do what you value regardless of your age!

What will you learn

- 1 What are some wellness therapies
- 2 Healthy Ageing and the role of the community: Age-friendly initiatives

Age-Friendly Community

- Have you thought about how when we get older, we often spend more time in our homes and communities? And so the environment plays a significant role on our health, wellbeing and the quality of our lives.
- That is why we need to work together to remove the barriers that deter older people from participating in their communities.
- We need to make sure that those who are less mobile or not online are not left behind. Let's get into it?

Activity 4

Friends and neighbours

Take action!

The Covid-19 pandemic showed us how much we need a good support network. Let's learn some lessons from this event.

Be a change agent in your community! Do you know someone who may need your help or support? Lay a hand!

Activity 4: Friends and neighbours

1**2****3**

My community

Reflect on your past experiences as a neighbour.

How was your life growing up? Were you close with your neighbours? Did you have a good sense of community?

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 5**

How was your sense of community growing up?

- I was satisfied with my local area
- I walked every day (took the bus) to school with my neighbours
- I went over to my neighbour's for lunch or dinner
- I grew up with a good sense of community
- I felt supported by the members of my community
- I knew my neighbours
- Whenever there was a problem, my neighbours and I stuck together to come up with a solution
- I borrowed things from neighbours
- I chatted with my neighbours once a month (at least!)

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 5**

What about today? How is your sense of community?

- I walk with my neighbours
- I feel supported by the members of my community
- I have a good sense of community
- I am satisfied with my local area
- I go over to my neighbour's for lunch or dinner
- I exchange favours with my neighbours
- I chat with my neighbours once a month
- I support others in the community
- I know my neighbours
- I borrow things from neighbours

Activity 4: Friends and neighbours

1

2

3

Search for activities in your community

What makes an age-friendly community? Having available events for everyone! These activities provide things for people to do and are fun ways to meet your new neighbors and find out what your local community is passionate about!

Activity 4: Friends and neighbours

1

2

3

How can you find these activities?

Look up events in your area (Facebook, Newsletters, Agenda) or stop by local businesses and take note of events listed on their bulletin boards!

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

HEALTHY **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 5**

What did you find out?
Create your list of the activities in your neighbourhood!
Write them in topics below:

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 HEALTHY **MODULE 2** **CHAPTER 5**

What do you think of these events?

- I know many people who usually attend these events
- I don't know anyone there
- They are expensive
- Affordable
- They are not interesting
- The event is age-friendly and designed for all people
- They are too far away
- Nearby
- Interesting

Activity 4: Friends and neighbours

Be the Change (Agent) you want to see in the world!

How about taking matters into your own hands?

Plan a (small) block party, a picnic in the park, a house party, whatever suits you and your community!

What's next?

Activity 4: Friends and neighbours

4

5

6

Save the date

Pick a special occasion (for example, Neighbour's European day, every last Friday of May). This way, it'll be easier to catch the public's attention!

Activity 4: Friends and neighbours

4

5

6

Pick the place

How's the weather outside? Can you meet at the local park? Provide the table/chairs and invite others to bring food. This way, each person will be responsible for bringing the food/drinks!

Activity 4: Friends and neighbours

4

5

6

Spread the news

Create a Facebook event and invite your friends!

Print some posters and distribute them through town! Or go for a walk and talk to those whom you encounter!

Activity 4: Friends and neighbours

If the event is successful, start thinking about making it a thing. You can begin with 10 people and the event can grow to a 100 people!

Our pick: Friends and neighbours in Portugal

In 2015, the *Boa Vizinhança Santo António* Association, *Associação Boa Vizinhança Santo António*, in Lisbon, Portugal, organized a party in a local garden to mark European Neighbour's Day. This event aimed to strengthen ties between those who live in *Santo António* Parish Council.

Between 12 pm and 10pm there were local handicrafts, and gastronomy, live music, raffle tickets, face painting, etc. Free entrance.

Members of the *Santo António* Parish Council were there to clarify any doubts of population about the services provided.

The funds resulting from the sale of raffle tickets or donations were distributed to social support associations in the Parish Council .

[Learn more \(PT\)](#)

Wellness therapies

Our journey through lifestyle and therapies has gone over some important steps: healthy eating, exercising, safe use of medication, spending quality time with friends and neighbours, and now we arrive the last stop in this module.

Here are some of the activities you can do on your own, or in a group environment, to help you relax, address some of your anxiety, feelings of loneliness, among others. Are there any of these activities in your community?

Wellness therapies

What do you already know about therapies? Have you heard of any of these?

Yoga

Yoga focuses on strength, flexibility and breathing. The series of movements designed to increase strength and flexibility and breathing, to boost physical and mental wellbeing.

Tai chi

Tai chi is a low-impact exercise, that can reduce stress, improve posture, balance and general mobility, and increase muscle strength in the legs

Mindfulness

Remind yourself to take notice of your thoughts, feelings, body sensations and the world around you. This is first step to mindfulness

Wellness therapies

Have you ever enrolled in some of these activities? Do you know someone who has? How was your/their experience like?

Acting classes

This group activity fights loneliness, fosters creativity and helps with your exercise intake!

Book club

If you like to read and would like to meet others that feel the same, you could join a book club. You can meet new people and share some ideas on all kinds of literature!

Dance classes

Maybe this is the option that suits you best. Each activity can work differently for everyone. Would you like to exercise in a group setting and complete a dance routine to your favourite tune?

Wellness therapies

What about this hands-on therapies?

Painting

Painting allows you an immense amount of freedom. It can reduce stress levels and explore confused or difficult thoughts and feelings

Crayons or chalk

Painting seems too complex? Use crayons and chalk instead. They can instill happy memories from your childhood.

Sculpting

Much of sculpting involves trial and error, so don't worry too much, this is about experimenting with different concepts and materials!

Wellness therapies

We can't change the world, but we can start by improving the community which we live in. Here are some ways to stay connected and look after yourself and your neighbours!

Community gardening

A community garden can have various benefits for your health: connecting with other people, staying active and growing your fresh food, maintaining a healthy and balanced diet, etc. What are your thoughts on this practice?

Absence doesn't make the heart go fonder

Don't let your busy schedule get in the way of you dropping by your neighbour/friend and say hello! Don't have time to stop by? Send a text message or give them a call!

Get a move on

Why not visit places where you can be around other people – for example, a park, a café, the public library, the church, the mosque. Consider joining a group or class that focuses on something you enjoy. Any thoughts?

Activity 5: Develop a community garden

All talk and no action? Let's get our hands (on) dirty!

What about setting up a community garden?

This is a way to:

- enjoy nature
- connect with other people
- get active outdoors
- get a new perspective on what you're eating and the entire food chain

Activity 5: Develop a community garden

- Identify a location
- Speak with the local council or any landowner you might know whose land is not being put to use
- Request permission to begin a garden on this land
- Set a budget. How could you raise some more money? Think about holding a fundraiser
- Get in touch with local groups, businesses, schools to present your idea and the benefits of a community garden project

Activity 5: Develop a community garden

- Establish a volunteer community to manage the project: start recruiting by putting up a poster on the bulletin board of the supermarket, for example. Why not share a post on Facebook groups that might be interested in this topic?
- Hear the local gardeners, landscapers or builders. Would they be interested in lending a hand to your project?
- Are you interested in learning more about business and other service(s) opportunities you can provide? Head over to the Business modules!

Read more

Here's a community garden success story in Coimbra, Portugal.

Think about it, are there any community gardens where you live? Would you be interested in participating in one?

Hands full and hands-on: list of useful contacts and services

Do you feel like trying some of these activities? Would you invite an older person you know to join you? Here are some wellness groups that welcome everyone in the community! Be inspired!

✓ Outdoor yoga:

https://yogacoimbra.com/featured_item/yoga-no-botnico/ (PT)

✓ Tai Chi:

<https://www.facebook.com/TaiChiChuanCoimbra/> (PT)

✓ Book club:

<https://www.uc.pt/org/centrodramaturgia/12> (PT)

✓ Acting classes:

<https://oteatrao.com/evento/classes-de-teatro/> (PT)

Mental wellbeing matters

These were some examples of what a person can do to reduce anxiety, de-stress and engage in activities with others. If you feel like you or someone you know might need further help from a health professional, do:

- ✓ Contact your GP
- ✓ Look for local groups and organisations that can support you and provide counselling
- ✓ Call a support line
- ✓ Seek talking therapies, or psychological therapies

Chapter summary

1

You learned more about some wellness therapies

2

You were reminded of the role of the community in one's social participation

3

You now have a list of contacts and services that should encourage you to stay active

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You've learned more about wellness therapies

2

You'll have a broad overview of well-being and healthy relationships

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)

Module summary

1 Healthy eating

2 Daily and weekly tips
for planning nutritionally balanced meals

3 Tips for a healthy diet on a budget

4 Exercise: Tips for adults aged 19 to 64 and
adults aged 65 and over

5 Safe use of medication

6 Sense of community: support in
the neighbourhood and wellness therapies

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You learned more about healthy eating, exercise and medication

2

You got know more about wellness therapies

3

You completed activities that can help you be a change agent for your own health and others in the community

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this module or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

[Restart](#)[Next](#)